

Supplementary Tables and Figures

Table S1. Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristics at different heights for year 2016-17.

Height (m)	Method	k	c (m/s)	V _{avg} (m/s)	P/A (W/m ²)	E/A (kWh/m ²)	V _{mp} (m/s)	V _{me} (m/s)
80	EML	2.6294	7.8718	6.9942	305.3760	2675.0930	6.5620	9.7610
	EMJ	2.6294	7.8711	6.9936	305.2910	2674.3490	6.5610	9.7600
	EPF	2.6404	7.8700	6.9936	304.4360	2666.8590	6.5720	9.7440
	MoM	2.6216	7.8718	6.9936	305.9060	2679.7410	6.5540	9.7720
	MMLM	2.6469	7.8584	6.9838	302.6580	2651.2810	6.5690	9.7200
	GM	2.3748	7.8928	6.9955	329.0590	2882.5610	6.2700	10.2080
60	EML	2.6227	7.2799	6.4678	241.8980	2119.0250	6.0620	9.0360
	EMJ	2.6227	7.2792	6.4672	241.8270	2118.4070	6.0620	9.0350
	EPF	2.6100	7.2803	6.4672	242.6310	2125.4490	6.0500	9.0530
	MoM	2.6149	7.2799	6.4672	242.3210	2122.7360	6.0540	9.0460
	MMLM	2.6173	7.2685	6.4573	241.0560	2111.6530	6.0470	9.0290
	GM	2.4126	7.3134	6.4839	258.8210	2267.2730	5.8580	9.3930
40	EML	2.5104	6.5376	5.8012	179.9790	1576.6170	5.3400	8.2560
	EMJ	2.5104	6.5365	5.8002	179.8850	1575.7960	5.3390	8.2550
	EPF	2.4765	6.5386	5.8002	181.6790	1591.5070	5.3060	8.3040
	MoM	2.5016	6.5371	5.8002	180.3420	1579.7970	5.3310	8.2680
	MMLM	2.4866	6.5337	5.7963	180.7750	1583.5890	5.3130	8.2840
	GM	2.4491	6.5511	5.8098	184.0980	1612.7020	5.2880	8.3590
20	EML	2.2454	5.3848	4.7694	109.1610	956.2500	4.1420	7.1510
	EMJ	2.2454	5.3828	4.7677	109.0390	955.1800	4.1400	7.1480
	EPF	2.2112	5.3833	4.7677	110.4830	967.8280	4.1000	7.2040
	MoM	2.2347	5.3830	4.7677	109.4820	959.0650	4.1280	7.1660
	MMLM	2.2427	5.3944	4.7779	109.8560	962.3370	4.1460	7.1680
	GM	2.4187	5.3785	4.7686	102.7640	900.2110	4.3140	6.9000

Table S2. Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristics at different heights for year 2017-18.

Height (m)	Method	k	c (m/s)	V _{avg} (m/s)	P/A (W/m ²)	E/A (kWh/m ²)	V _{mp} (m/s)	V _{me} (m/s)
80	EML	2.6239	7.7292	6.8656	290.0820	2541.1183	6.4190	9.6170
	EMJ	2.6239	7.7284	6.8649	289.9880	2540.2949	6.4180	9.6160
	EPF	2.6086	7.7281	6.8649	289.7950	2538.6042	6.4210	9.6120
	MoM	2.6160	7.7291	6.8649	290.6000	2545.6560	6.4100	9.6280
	MMLM	2.6167	7.7194	6.8576	288.3530	2525.9723	6.4210	9.5910
	GM	2.3880	7.7574	6.8762	310.6070	2720.9173	6.1810	10.0090
60	EML	2.6060	7.0995	6.3076	223.8980	1961.3465	5.9130	8.8110
	EMJ	2.6060	7.0988	6.3070	223.8330	1960.7771	5.9120	8.8100
	EPF	2.5915	7.1015	6.3070	225.7420	1977.4999	5.8840	8.8550

	MoM	2.5980	7.0995	6.3070	224.2900	1964.7804	5.9060	8.8210
	MMLM	2.6155	7.0956	6.3036	223.8910	1961.2852	5.9030	8.8150
	GM	2.5437	7.1018	6.3040	228.3730	2000.5475	5.8360	8.9210
40	EML	2.5018	6.3274	5.6142	163.2410	1429.9912	5.1600	8.0020
	EMJ	2.5018	6.3263	5.6132	163.1530	1429.2203	5.1590	8.0010
	EPF	2.4430	6.3297	5.6132	166.0460	1454.5630	5.1030	8.0860
	MoM	2.4930	6.3268	5.6132	163.5740	1432.9082	5.1510	8.0130
	MMLM	2.4734	6.3290	5.6140	164.5990	1441.8872	5.1330	8.0420
	GM	2.5796	6.3232	5.6151	159.8060	1399.9006	5.2280	7.8990
20	EML	2.2081	5.2012	4.6063	99.5860	872.3734	3.9580	6.9650
	EMJ	2.2081	5.1991	4.6045	99.4660	871.3222	3.9570	6.9620
	EPF	2.1462	5.1992	4.6045	102.0080	893.5901	3.8820	7.0660
	MoM	2.1972	5.1992	4.6045	99.8970	875.0977	3.9440	6.9800
	MMLM	2.2083	5.2149	4.6185	100.3740	879.2762	3.9690	6.9830
	GM	2.5000	5.2085	4.6213	91.0970	798.0097	4.2460	6.5890

Table S3. Seasonal Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristics at different heights for year 2017-18.

Season	Height (m)	k	c (m/s)	V _{avg} (m/s)	P/A (W/m ²)	E/A (kWh/m ²)	V _{mp} (m/s)	V _{me} (m/s)
Summer	80	3.153324571	9.222059573	8.253946271	440.301	972.184	8.1713	10.7765
	60	3.049270312	8.769347736	7.836543404	383.558	846.895	7.6978	10.3466
	40	2.915556764	8.205142592	7.318062846	320.296	707.214	7.1042	9.8151
	20	2.797178461	7.120259229	6.339999354	213.494	471.394	6.0787	8.6347
Autumn	80	2.729388045	6.674137086	5.937429882	182.199	397.923	5.6466	8.1633
	60	2.93606682	6.042093528	5.390452642	130.447	284.896	5.2432	7.2116
	40	3.086982739	5.220269521	4.66760452	82.381	179.919	4.5985	6.1371
	20	2.906051479	4.49460109	4.008134161	53.946	117.819	3.8874	5.3821
Winter	80	2.335747491	6.83593542	6.057249172	154.703	334.158	5.3813	8.9086
	60	2.737125426	5.994709489	5.33353478	94.273	203.629	5.0772	7.3249
	40	3.210642096	4.976629468	4.458055307	50.298	108.644	4.4305	5.7868
	20	2.271263395	4.193539505	3.714636403	36.507	78.854	3.248	5.5379
Spring	80	3.039144157	8.011708599	7.158420684	295.092	651.563	7.0259	9.462
	60	3.030165656	7.416328143	6.625571351	234.356	517.459	6.4981	8.7666

40	2.856405425	6.690526993	5.962211427	176.639	390.018	5.7536	8.0566
20	2.553572708	5.703888145	5.063644534	116.377	256.961	4.6952	7.1539

Figure S1. Weibull probability distributions at different heights; (a) 20 m, (b) 40 m, (c) 60 m, (d) 80 m for year 2017-18.